

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION AND MODELLING OF FAILURE AND DAMAGE BEHAVIOUR OF MULTI-LAYERED CARBON-FIBRE REINFORCED PEEK

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SUMMARY: To design structural components made of multi-layered carbon-fibre reinforced PEEK, an improved understanding of the detailed material behaviour is essential. The high lightweight potential of CF-PEEK composites can only be used optimally, if the anisotropic fibre reinforcement is orientated according to the acting loads. On the one hand, the component optimisation requires adapted analytical and numerical simulation techniques as well as suitable realistic failure criteria which take into account the occurring damage mechanisms. On the other hand, the anisotropic properties of these materials have to be determined experimentally.

Though the calculation of stress and strain distributions of complexly loaded composites with textile reinforcement has experienced a tremendous improvement, the determination of bearable combined fracture loads is still difficult because the current generalising fracture criteria do not consider the damage which occurs in the heterogeneous microstructure. This demands the development of realistic macro-mechanical failure criteria and suitable damage models taking into account the micro-structural material behaviour as well as different modes of fracture. New failure criteria like the action-plane related fracture criterion do not only consider the difference between fibre fracture and inter-fibre fracture, but further fracture types in the plane of reinforcement are also introduced. In the presented criteria, it is taken into consideration that, in accordance to the mechanical material behaviour and phenomenological observations, compressive stresses tend to prevent the formation of matrix cracks, while corresponding tensile stresses tend to increase this possibility. In this paper, these failure criteria will be combined with a suitable degradation model which includes the partially non-linear composite behaviour from the onset of damage.

Finally, the proposed method will be used exemplarily to characterize the strength and the failure behaviour of multi-layered carbon-fibre reinforced PEEK compounds. Therefore, several fracture tests with various specimens were performed applying adapted testing techniques. The manufacturing of multi-layered CF-PEEK specimens made of commingled-yarn textiles were realised using a high-temperature autoclave and a high temperature press at the Institut für Leichtbau und Kunststofftechnik.

KEYWORDS: Simulation, Failure, Damage, Textiles, Testing

INTRODUCTION

Complex material requirements for high-performance lightweight applications increasingly demand the use of hybrid material structures with properties tailored to the loading direction as monolithic materials are frequently unable to provide optimum conditions for these applications. A high potential for innovation in this respect is to be expected from the intelligent use of textile reinforcement in the development of load-adapted and failure-tolerant lightweight structures. The optimum utilisation of special variable-axial textile 3D reinforcement, in particular, could make a significant contribution to developments of highly innovative structures, which will be of great interest not only from a scientific-technical, but also from an economic point of view.

Essential features of variable-axial textile 3D reinforcements are reinforcing fibre layers, in which the reinforcing fibres can be matched to the actual loads and to the contours of the component. This permits more effective exploitation of the characteristic potential of the reinforcing fibres in the compound component.

The load-adapted and failure-tolerant construction of the directionally optimised textile reinforcement components is intended to open up a new generation of lightweight structures, as a fundamental element for further technological developments. In the field of materials research this gives rise to an excellent symbiosis of innovative reinforcing materials and design component applications.

The component optimisation requires adapted analytical and numerical simulation techniques as well as suitable realistic failure criteria which take into account the occurring damage mechanisms. The fundamental investigations presented in this paper are carried out with the transfer objective of developing modified failure criteria like the action plane related fracture criterion of PUCK/SCHÜRMAN, in order to be able to formulate new material degradation conditions to realise optimised structures with controllable, successive failure reactions in lightweight applications, for example for high-performance rotors in process engineering. The introduced model of PUCK/SCHÜRMAN will be experimentally verified to characterize the strength and the failure behaviour of multi-layered carbon-fibre reinforced PEEK compounds. Therefore several fracture tests with various tensile specimens were performed applying adapted testing techniques.

PROCESSING TECHNIQUES

The manufacturing of composites made of commingled hybrid yarn consisting of reinforcing carbon fibres and high-temperature (HT) thermoplastic polyetheretherketone (PEEK) matrix (Tab. 1) is performed using a HT-autoclave (Fig. 1) or a HT-press. Thermoplastic composite material components with maximum dimensions up to a length of 3.5 m and a diameter of 1.5 m can be realised with these technologies at the ILK.

Fig. 1: High-temperature autoclave

Fig. 2: CF-PEEK preform

	TORAYCA T300 JB	ZYEX, Type 4120
Count [tex]	198.00	46.00
Number of filaments	3000.00	30.00
Filament diameter [µm]	7.00	39.00
Density [g/cm³]	1.78	1.30
Maximum tensile force [N]	122.70	16.04
Maximum tensile strain [%]	0.84	131.70
Maximum tensile force per count [cN/tex]	61.97	34.87
Tensile strength [MPa]	1062.76	100.00
Young's modulus [GPa]	230.00	3.70
Shrinkage at 200 °C	-	8.40

Tab. 1: Basic materials for the manufacturing of hybrid yarns [11]

Commingled hybrid yarns have a high potential for a homogeneous distribution of reinforcement and matrix filaments over the yarn cross section [9]. The desired ratio of fibre to matrix can be achieved by variation of the number of yarns during the hybrid yarn production (Tab. 2). Uni-directional (UD) and bi-directional (BD) carbon fibre reinforced PEEK composite specimens were fabricated from commin-

gled yarn with Torayca fibres (Tab. 1) using the HT-pressing technique.

Material	Type	Initial count [tex]	Quantity	Final count [tex]
CF	TORAYCA, T300 JB	198	2	396
PEEK	ZYEX, Type 4120	46	4	184
			Total	580

Tab. 2: Combination of matrix- and reinforcement components [11]

Description	NWM 3-008-1	NWM 3-009-1	NWM 3-010-1	NWM 3-011-1
Layup	0°/90°	0°/-60°/90°	0°/60°/90°	0°/±45°/90°
$m_{A,theor}$ [g/m ²]	573.49	851.53	851.53	1124.81
$m_{A,stitching\ yarn}$ [g/m ²]	18.7			
ϕ [vol.-%]	58.8			
ψ [weight-%]	65.8			

Tab. 3: Constructive design of the knitted reinforcing fabrics [11]

The warp yarn and the weft yarn of the knitted fabrics shown in Fig. 2 and Tab. 3 consist of CF-PEEK hybrid yarns. Solely, the stitching yarn is made of pure PEEK. During the HT-pressing process, the stitching yarn smelts with the PEEK matrix, so that the structure becomes a real multi-layered composite.

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

The material behaviour of CF-PEEK composites has not been investigated so far. However, for a reliable application for complex lightweight components, a realistic description of the failure behaviour and the successive degradation behaviour is particularly necessary. For this purpose, several tensile tests were performed to observe the phenomenological background of the material degradation process. Therefore, several composite plates were produced according to the restrictions in Tab. 4 from the fabrics listed in Tab. 3. To describe the failure behaviour in dependence of the fibre orientation, different loading directions per composite have been analysed (Fig. 3, Fig. 4).

Description	Layup	Textile Preform	Loading Direction
TN 26	0° wound		0°/45°/90°
TN 32a	[0/60/90/0/-60/90] _s	NWM 3-010-1 NWM 3-009-1	0°/30°/45°/60°/90°
TN 33	[0/30/90/0/-30/90] _s	NWM 3-010-1 NWM 3-009-1	0°/30°/45°/60°/90°
TN 34a	[90/60/0/90/-60/0] _s	NWM 3-010-1 NWM 3-009-1	0°/30°/45°/60°/90°
TN 35	[90/30/0/90/-30/0] _s	NWM 3-010-1 NWM 3-009-1	0°/30°/45°/60°/90°
TN 37	[0] ₁₂	NWM 3-011-1	0°/45°/90°
TN 38	[0/90/0/90/0/90] _s	NWM 3-008-1	0°/30°/45°/60°/90°
TN 41	[0/60/120] _s	Satin Fabric ¼	0°/30°/45°/60°/90°
TN 42	[0] ₆	Satin Fabric ¼	0°/30°/45°/60°/90°

Tab. 4: Overview of the tested specimens

In order to be able to verify the proposed failure criterion and the degradation model experimentally, it is necessary to develop adapted testing methods that enable a reliable multi-axial application of

loads. Therefore, testing methods were developed for tension/compression tests in various directions (T/C tests) [7].

The wealth of information that the directional T/C test supplies permits the first basic physical failure phenomena to be explained and subsequently also documents the deficiencies of the global failure criteria. In the T/C tests the failure-critical stress combination along the prescribed loading direction was produced by a strain-controlled multi-axial test machine with adapted long-range strain twist extensometer (Fig. 5). This extensometer permits the strain to be recorded as well as the gradual progress of failure. The tests carried out on the CF-PEEK tensile specimens serve, on the one hand, to determine fracture stresses as well as the related fracture angle and, on the other hand, to characterise the elementary fracture types.

Fig. 3: CF-PEEK-plate TN 42 with tensile specimens

Fig. 4: Manufacturing of the tensile specimens

Fig. 5: Tensile test: testing facility

Fig. 6: Tensile test: fracture of the specimen

FAILURE BEHAVIOUR AND MATERIAL DEGRADATION

Background

To describe the structural mechanical fracture behaviour of anisotropic fibre-reinforced multi-layered composites or textile-reinforced composites, respectively, a significant number of failure criteria were developed. In comparison to global interactive failure criteria, which link various failure modes into one single failure criterion, physically based failure criteria denote a substantial progress [1], because

they are able to describe the prevailing fracture modes independently by means of adapted fracture conditions. Nevertheless, these criteria only allow the characterisation of the first ply failure. They do not provide any information concerning the successive failure behaviour and the resultant degradation of the laminate stiffness values. Though, in recent years first investigation has been undertaken to determine the damage mechanisms and the degradation behaviour of fibre reinforced composites [13]. PUCK/SCHÜRMAN proposed a phenomenological failure and degradation model [3] on the basis of physically based failure criteria and applied this model to composites made of glass fibre reinforced epoxy resin. Thereby, the stress-strain analysis takes place with the help of the classical laminate theory (CLT). Based on the assumption that the failure behaviour of a cracked layer can be treated mesoscopically smeared, the engineering constants of the affected layer(s) are attenuated after the detection of first ply failure, e. g. depending upon the acting load or occurring deformation. LANGKAMP proposed a method that enables the use of physically based failure criteria for the description of the fracture of textile-reinforced composites with various matrix systems [7]. HUFENBACH et al. have shown the adaptability of this method to describe the degradation behaviour of braided composites [8] and of glass-fibre reinforced multi-layered composites [12].

Action-Plane Related Failure Criterion

Experiments show that the failure of CF-PEEK composite structures initially takes place at the heterogeneous micro-level. The development of a new type of so called action plane related fracture criteria, which considers the microscopic failure mechanisms, enables a physically based description of the prevailing failure modes of the experimentally analysed CF-PEEK composites. On this account, the meso-mechanical action-plane criterion of HASHIN/PUCK [2] is applied here to the failure analysis of multi-layered carbon-fibre reinforced CF-PEEK structures by using it together with the equivalent single-layer model.

In order to formulate the action-plane related fracture criterion for an evaluation of the critical stress states, HASHIN/PUCK have embarked on a novel approach in respect of the standard generalising interaction criteria. This criterion allows for not only the difference between the fracture modes „fibre failure“ (FF) and „inter-fibre failure“ (IFF), but also incorporates a fracture angle as a free parameter that characterises further fracture modes in the fibre-parallel plane. On the basis of the assumption that fracture is determined by the stresses of the fracture plane, the criterion records the failure modes FF and IFF by different failure conditions, which take into account only the acting stresses in the fracture plane.

To characterise the fracture modes and mechanisms by using the fracture mode criteria it is convenient to introduce a fibre-oriented local coordinate system x_1, n, t . The location of the coordinate system is defined by the rotational angle θ_B around the fibre-parallel axis x_1 (Fig. 2), whereas the fracture angle θ_b is directly included in the failure criteria.

Fig. 7

Definition of stress components and coordinate systems

The main reasons for fibre failure are fibre breakage under tensional load and fibre buckling under compression. This assumes that the fibre failure is solely initiated by the fibre-parallel stress σ_1^\pm and remains unaffected by other stresses that occur. For the mathematical description of the fibre failure, a maximum normal stress criterion is applied

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{R_{\parallel}^\pm} \right)^2 = 1,$$

whereas R_{\parallel}^+ represents the axial tensile strength ($\sigma_1 > 0$) and R_{\parallel}^- the axial compressive strength respectively.

The fracture conditions for IFF are, in comparison to the FF criterion, clearly more complex as different types of failure such as adhesive failure of the fibre-matrix interface or cohesive failure of the matrix as well as different failure modes such as tension, longitudinal shear and cross-sectional shear failure need to be realistically described. It can be shown that by adopting an approach based on the strain energy release rate, a fracture criterion can be developed for combined fracture modes. The failure initially occurs parallel to the fibres in a plane variable with the fracture angle θ_B . The associated failure criterion then yields in the following general formulation

$$\max_{\theta} F(\sigma_n, \tau_{nt}, \tau_{n1}) = 1.$$

Furthermore, it is observed that in accordance with the expected mechanical properties of the material and the phenomenological effects, compression stresses vertical to the fibres prevent inter-fibre failure. The other stresses $\sigma_1, \sigma_t, \tau_{t1}$ acting perpendicular to the fibre-parallel fracture planes do not affect the failure behaviour. The normal and shear stresses that arise then are related to each other by means of a quadratic polynomial.

- Tensile stresses ($\sigma_n \geq 0$): IFF is initiated by a combination of the acting tensile stress σ_n and the shear stresses τ_{nt} and τ_{n1} in the fracture plane

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_n}{R_{\perp}^+} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{nt}}{R_{\perp\perp}^A} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{n1}}{R_{\perp\parallel}} \right)^2 = 1.$$

- Compressive stresses ($\sigma_n < 0$): IFF is initiated by the shear stresses τ_{nt} and τ_{n1} in the fracture plane and prevented by the compressive stress σ_n

$$\left(\frac{\tau_{nt}}{R_{\perp\perp}^A - p_{\perp\perp} \sigma_n} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{n1}}{R_{\perp\parallel} - p_{\perp\parallel} \sigma_n} \right)^2 = 1.$$

The proportional coefficients $p_{\perp\perp}$ and $p_{\perp\parallel}$ gather the effect of the axial stress σ_n on the failure in the compression domain. These coefficients have to be determined experimentally as well as the resistance in the action plane $R_{\perp\perp}^A$, that must not be replaced by the strength $R_{\perp\perp}$.

In the case of a two-dimensional stress state, which arises from the tensile tests presented in this investigation, the failure criteria simplify as follows:

- Tensile stresses ($\sigma_n \geq 0$): The fracture angle is always $\Phi_{fp} = 0^\circ$.

$$f_{IFF} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\tau_{21}}{R_{\perp\parallel}^A} \right)^2 + \left(1 - \frac{p_{\perp\parallel}^{(+)}}{R_{\perp\parallel}^A} R_{\perp\perp}^{(+),A} \right) \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{R_{\perp\perp}^{(+),A}} \right)^2} + \frac{p_{\perp\parallel}^{(+)}}{R_{\perp\parallel}^A} \sigma_2 + \left| \frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_{1D}} \right| = 1.$$

- Compressive stresses ($\sigma_n < 0$) and $0 \leq \frac{\sigma_2}{\tau_{21}} \leq \frac{R_{\perp\perp}^A}{|\tau_{21c}|}$: The fracture angle is always $\Phi_{fp} = 0^\circ$.

$$f_{IFF} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\tau_{21}}{R_{\perp\parallel}^A} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{p_{\perp\parallel}^{(-)}}{R_{\perp\parallel}^A} \right)^2} \sigma_2^2 + \frac{p_{\perp\parallel}^{(-)}}{R_{\perp\parallel}^A} \sigma_2 + \left| \frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_{1D}} \right| = 1.$$

- Compressive stresses ($\sigma_n < 0$) and $0 \leq \frac{|\tau_{21}|}{|\sigma_2|} \leq \frac{|\tau_{21c}|}{R_{\perp\perp}^A}$:

$$f_{IFF} = \cos \Theta \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_2}{R_{\perp\perp}^A}\right)^2 (1 - \cos^2 \Theta) + \left(\frac{\tau_{21}}{R_{\perp\perp}^A}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{p_{\perp\perp}^{(-)}}{R_{\perp\perp}^A}\right)^2 \sigma_2^2 \cos^2 \Theta} + \frac{p_{\perp\perp}^{(-)}}{R_{\perp\perp}^A} \sigma_2 \cos^2 \Theta + \left|\frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_{1D}}\right| = 1.$$

Description of the material degradation after first-ply failure

After the occurrence of first microcracks in the PEEK matrix, the stiffnesses of the affected layer will be reduced with increasing load. According to the degradation model of PUCK/SCHÜRMAN [3], the degradation of the engineering constants of the damaged UD-layer is controlled by the self-reducing function

$$\eta = \frac{1}{f_{IFF}}.$$

Depending on the fracture mode, the degradation function η will be used to attenuate the engineering constants E_{\perp} , $G_{\parallel\perp}$ and $\nu_{\parallel\perp}$ (for $\sigma_n \geq 0$) or $G_{\parallel\perp}$ and $\nu_{\parallel\perp}$ (for $\sigma_n < 0$), respectively (Tab. 5).

When compressive stresses occur in the fracture plane, E_{\perp} will be retain unchanged, because the presence of cracks does not constrict the stress transfer. The flowchart of the degradation process is displayed in Fig. 8.

$\sigma_n \geq 0$	Engineering constants		
	E_{\parallel}	$E_{\parallel} = E_{\parallel}^0$ until fibre failure	
	E_{\perp}	$E_{\perp} = f(E_{\perp}^0, \eta)$	$E_{\perp} = E_{\perp}^0$
	$G_{\parallel\perp}$	$G_{\parallel\perp} = f(G_{\parallel\perp}^0, \eta)$	
	$\nu_{\parallel\perp}$	$\nu_{\parallel\perp} = f(\nu_{\parallel\perp}^0, \eta)$	

Tab 5: Material degradation scheme

Fig 8: Flowchart of the failure calculation

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

With the accomplished tensile tests, a huge database for the load-deformation behaviour of different CF-PEEK textile composites has been established. The introduced failure and degradation model will be exemplarily verified using results of the tensile tests carried out on the specimens TN 32a and TN 38. The input parameters for the failure analysis E_{\parallel} , E_{\perp} , $G_{\parallel\perp}$ and $\nu_{\parallel\perp}$ have been determined on the TN 37 tensile specimen. The input data for the calculation of the degradation behaviour with the PUCK/SCHÜRMAN model are given below in Tab. 6.

Experimentally observed		Assumptions and Calculations [7]		
UD engineering constants	Strengths	Carbon Fibre Data TORAYCA T300 JB	Strengths	Slope parameters
$E_{\parallel} = 110360 \text{ MPa}$	$R_{\parallel}^{(+)} = 1126 \text{ MPa}$	$E_{f\parallel} = 230 \text{ GPa}$	$R_{\parallel}^{(-)} = 800 \text{ MPa}$	$p_{\perp\parallel}^{(+)} = 0.6$
$E_{\perp} = 8870 \text{ MPa}$	$R_{\perp}^{(+)} = 37 \text{ MPa}$	$\nu_{f\parallel\perp} = 0.28$	$R_{\perp}^{(-)} = 200 \text{ MPa}$	$p_{\perp\parallel}^{(-)} = 0.7$
$G_{\parallel\perp} = 5000 \text{ MPa}$	$R_{\perp\parallel} = 79 \text{ MPa}$		$R_{\perp\parallel}^A = 63.9 \text{ MPa}$	$p_{\perp\parallel}^{(+)} = 0.566$
$\nu_{\parallel\perp} = 0.373$				

Tab. 6: CF-PEEK input data

Fig. 10 shows the experimentally observed tensile load-strain curves in comparison to the predicted curves from the PUCK/SCHÜRMAN model. For the specimens from the TN 32a series, the curves resulting from the loading directions 45°, 60° and 90° are plotted, whereas only the loading direction 90° is displayed for the specimen from the TN 38 series. It could be observed that the experimental data shows no significant scatter. Solely, the fracture stresses partly differ up to 10% from each other. Thereby, a premature failure was observed near the clamping of the specimens, leading to a substantial reduction of the measured fracture stress and explaining this observed phenomenon.

The measured curves have been approximated by the load-strain curve resulting from the failure calculation in a good manner. The predicted stress where the first IFF occurs particularly coincides with the observations made in the tensile tests. The failure and degradation model from PUCK/SCHÜRMAN tends to predict an overestimated fracture stress as the model was developed for laminates originally. Thus, possible weakening of the textile CF-PEEK preform in the process of manufacturing could not be considered in the introduced model.

The deviation between calculated and measured fracture stress for the various composites and loading directions averages up to 8%. All predicted curves show higher stress values than the experimentally obtained curves at the same strain level. To draw a conclusion, it could be noticed that the underlying UD engineering constants have overstated values. These constants have been determined on the specimens from the TN 37 series, which were produced with the same process of manufacturing, but exhibit a different preform material than the tested specimens.

Another observed phenomenon is the non-linear load-strain curve already from the initial point of the curve. But the degradation model of PUCK/SCHÜRMAN describes a curve linearity until the first IFF occurs. Thus, a starting point for enhancements of the model is to consider the effects leading to a material degradation before the first IFF occurs (e. g. microcracking).

Fig 9: Experimental and theoretical load-strain curves

CONCLUSIONS

This investigation considers the attributes of CF-PEEK composite failure criteria necessary for use in the design of complex lightweight applications where the need for reliable prediction of performance must be balanced by simplicity and ease of use. Therefore, new so called action-plane related fracture criteria were applied and modified to describe the failure behaviour of CF-PEEK composite structures under tensile loading conditions. The failure criteria were combined with a suitable degradation model that uses a simple but realistic way of damage description. The introduced model includes fibre failure

and inter-fibre failure as well as non-linear stress-strain behaviour. Thus, the failure analysis becomes more realistic than it has been with other methods used today in advanced engineering. The performed experiments show that the proposed method could describe the complex damage behaviour of CF-PEEK composite structures in a realistic way. Experimental data that will allow to improve the simplifying assumptions will be made available in the next phase of the investigation. In detail, a further experimental validation concerning the exact failure mechanisms to describe the material degradation behaviour will be necessary. Additional work needs to be done to identify the most appropriate load transfer mechanisms. Therefore, the specimens will be analysed using acoustic emission techniques in the next step of the study.

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